

Original Article

Policies on the use of artificial intelligence adopted by journals in psychiatry and mental health

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Compliance with regulations on ethics

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Abstract

Background: The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in academic publishing is expanding rapidly, raising concerns about authorship, transparency, and editorial standards. Although organisations such as Committee on Publication Ethics and International Council of Medical Journal Editors have proposed guidelines on the use of AI, the extent to which they have been adopted by journals in psychiatry and mental health remains unclear.

Objectives: To examine the adoption and content of AI policies in psychiatry and mental health journals indexed in SCImago and to determine whether higher-quartile journals are more likely to include policies related to AI.

Methods: Policies related to AI in the guidelines for authors and reviewers were examined for two groups of journals, all indexed under *Psychiatry* and *Mental Health* in SCImago in November-December 2024. The two groups were (1) a stratified random sample of 200 journals (50 per quartile) chosen from a total of 578 journals and (2) 25 top-ranked journals in psychiatry and mental health.

Results: Among the first group, 78 (39%) journals included policies related to AI in their guidelines or instructions for authors and reviewers, the number being greater in top-quartile journals (56% in Q1 versus 20% in Q4; $\chi^2 = 14$, $P = .003$). Of the 78 journals, 69 (88.5%) disallowed AI tools as named authors, an equal number mandated disclosure of the use of AI, and 58 (74.4%) emphasised author accountability. Peer review policies mostly prohibited AI use ($n = 47$); AI-assisted copy editing was permitted in 56 journals; and policies on AI-generated images varied. None reported using AI detection tools. Among the top 25 journals, 16 (64%) included policies related to AI; all prohibited authorship to AI and required disclosure; and one reported using AI detection tools.

Conclusion: Despite the rising use of AI in publishing, most psychiatry and mental health journals, especially the lower-quartile journals, lack policies on such use. Wider adoption and standardisation of policies related to AI are crucial to ensure research integrity and credibility.

Keywords:

AI policy, artificial intelligence, large language models, psychiatry, publishing ethics

Introduction

Chatbots such as ChatGPT, which use AI (artificial intelligence) and are built on large language models, offer enhanced efficiency and convenience for scholarly work.^{1,2} Recent surveys highlight the growing popularity of AI chatbots among researchers. An international survey involving more than 2000 medical researchers from 95 countries found that 44.5% used AI chatbots in research, mostly for writing or editing manuscripts, with 62% of the respondents viewing AI chatbots as helpful for general administrative tasks.³ Another survey of more than 2300 researchers representing various regions, disciplines, and career stages showed that 76% had used AI in their research-related activities.⁴ With the rapid advances and growing use of AI technology internationally, the ethical and practical implications of the use of AI for academic publishing need to be regularly explored.

A range of ethical concerns have been raised about the use of AI in scientific publishing, particularly regarding authorship, attribution, copyright, plagiarism, and potential biases.^{1,2} Researchers may use AI to increase their rate of research output and, without adequate human oversight, the proliferation of such content may compromise the integrity and validity of scientific publications.^{5,6} Groups such as the Committee of Publication Ethics (COPE), International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), and World Association of Medical Editors have proposed guidelines regarding the use of AI within the publishing process.⁷⁻⁹ Perkins and Roe conducted a thematic analysis of publisher guidelines on AI use and identified six themes: confining authorship only to humans (and not to any other entities including AI tools), author accountability, disclosure and transparency, research integrity, fluid policies, and constraints and exclusions.¹⁰

Given the potential for unethical use of AI in scientific publishing, all scientific journals and publishers need to provide clear guidelines to authors and reviewers regarding the use of AI.¹¹ However, by the end of 2023, only 56 out of 162 (34.6%) publishers affiliated to the International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers had a publicly available AI policy.¹² According to Ganjavi et al., among the top 100 *publishers* in terms of size, only 24 provided an AI guideline, of which 15 were among the top 25 publishers; in contrast, among the top 100 *journals*, 87 provided guidance on AI.¹³ Similarly, Lund et al.¹⁴ reported that among the top 300 academic journals, more than half had an AI policy. Only a few studies have focused on specific disciplines. A study of ophthalmology journals indexed in PubMed found that among the 84 journals in the field, 53 (63.1%) had AI policies, and that journals with AI policies had higher metrics including the impact factor and SCImago Journal Rank (SJR).¹⁵ Although journals tend to adopt the publishing policies of their publishers, substantial variability was observed in AI policies even among journals published by the same publisher.¹³

The use of AI has been increasing in psychiatric research in recent years.¹⁶ The implications of AI for academic publishing specifically within the field of psychiatry have also been discussed, and largely reflect the general concerns raised in academia in general.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Mental health researchers, editors, and reviewers of journals in psychiatry need to keep themselves abreast of advancements in AI and their implications for scientific publishing. Unless psychiatry journals provide clear guidelines on the use of AI, there is a risk of unethical and improper use that could compromise the scientific validity and ethical integrity of publications in this field. This study therefore aims to (1) examine the current adoption of AI policies in psychiatry

and mental health journals across all four SCImago quartiles, (2) summarise the content of these policies, and (3) assess whether higher-quartile journals are more likely to include AI policies.

Methods

Selection of journals

All journals indexed under *Psychiatry and Mental Health* in SCImago (a public portal reporting journal- and country-level indicators based on the Scopus® database) were reviewed, as recorded in its 2023 list, on 3 November 2024 and then divided into two categories: (1) a stratified random sample of 200 journals (50 per quartile) out of the 578 journals listed and (2) top 25 journals in psychiatry and mental health. SCImago ranks journals using SJR, which takes into account both citation counts and the prestige of citing journals. Quartiles are assigned by dividing the ordered list into four groups: Q1 (top 25%), Q2, Q3, and Q4 (bottom 25%).

The random sample of 200 journals was to estimate the proportion of journals adopting AI policies with a margin of error of $\pm 5.5\%$ at a 95% confidence level. For the random selection, random numbers were generated from the website <https://www.random.org>. Ten of the top 25 journals also featured in the 50 journals selected randomly from Q1. The study methodology was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework.²⁰ The journal selection process is summarised in Figure 1.

Data extraction

In November-December 2024, two reviewers independently extracted the details of policies related to the use of AI from the guidelines for authors and reviewers available on the official website of each journal. Disagreements between the two reviewers were resolved

with inputs from the principal investigator. The information extracted for each selected journal is summarised in Table 1.

Ethics

Ethical approval was not required for this study as it involved analysis of publicly accessible information (journal policies) and did not include human participants, animals, or identifiable personal data.

Data synthesis and analysis

Extracted policy data from the journals were qualitatively synthesised. We used chi-square tests to ascertain whether some characteristics of a given journal (quartile, affiliation with a major publisher, origin from the United States or the UK) made it more likely or less likely to include AI policies.

Results

Characteristics of selected journals

Characteristics of the 200 randomly selected journals and those of the top 25 are summarised in Table 2. Among the 200 journals, the leading publishers were Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley, Sage, Routledge, Cambridge University Press, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, Taylor & Francis, American Psychological Association, and Emerald Publishing; these publishers accounted for 60% of the journals. Most journals were based in the United States ($n=62$) or the United Kingdom ($n=61$). The combined representation of the two countries was 82% in Q1, 72% in Q2, 68% in Q3, and 24% in Q4 journals.

Among the top 25 journals, the leading publishers were Elsevier, Wiley, Springer Nature, and Taylor & Francis. Except for one journal from Switzerland, all the others were from either the United States or the United Kingdom.

Figure 1. Identification and selection of journals for artificial intelligence policy review.

Adoption of policies on the use of artificial intelligence

Of the 200 journals, 78 (39%; 95% CI: 33.5%–44.5%) included policies on the use of AI within the guidelines for authors or reviewers; among the top 25, 16 (64%) had such policies.

Higher-quartile journals were more likely to have AI policies ($\chi^2=14, P=.003$): 56% of Q1, 42% of Q2, 36% of Q3, and 20% of Q4 journals had such policies. Among the 120 journals published by the top ten publishers, 59 (49.2%) included AI policies, compared to 19 (23.8%) of the 80 journals published by other publishers ($\chi^2=13, P<.001$). Journals based in the

United States or the UK were also more likely to include AI policies ($\chi^2=7.2, P=.007$): 46.3% of the 123 US/UK journals versus 27.3% of the journals published from elsewhere.

No artificial intelligence as author

Of the 78 journals that did include policies on the use of AI, 69 (88.5%) explicitly prohibited AI as a named author, typically citing the inability of AI tools to assume responsibility for submitted work (Table 3). The remaining nine did not state their position clearly. Among the top 25 journals, all 16 with AI policies explicitly prohibited AI authorship (Table 4).

Table 1. Elements related to artificial intelligence policy extracted from the guidelines to authors and reviewers given by the journals chosen for the study

Aspect of AI policy	Description
AI policy inclusion	Is policy on AI included in the guidelines?
Source guideline	Do the guidelines cite any other guideline on the use of AI? If so, which of these guidelines? (For example, ICMJE, COPE, or WAME)
Policy on AI tool as an author	Is authorship for AI tools allowed or prohibited?
Author accountability	Do the guidelines state that authors should be accountable for any AI-generated content in the manuscript?
Transparency and disclosure	Do the author guidelines require disclosure of the use of AI? If so, in which section or part of the manuscript should this disclosure be placed?
Research integrity	Do the author guidelines flag the potential risks of AI use on the quality and integrity of the work? Are authors required to discuss these issues within the manuscript?
Adaptability of policies	Do the guidelines state that the AI policies may be updated or revised in the future? If so, are updates to be expected at regular intervals?
Constraints and exclusions	Does the policy explicitly prohibit the use of AI?
AI-generated images	What is the journal's policy on the submission of images (figures, photographs, etc.) created by generative AI?
AI-assisted copy editing	What is the journal's policy on AI-assisted improvements to human-generated texts for readability, style, grammar, and spelling?
Peer review policy	Does the journal allow or prohibit peer reviewers to use AI?
AI detection tools	Does the journal use any AI detection tools to screen submissions for AI-generated content?

AI: artificial intelligence; COPE: Committee of Publication Ethics; ICMJE: International Committee of Medical Journal Editors; WAME: World Association of Medical Editors.

Author accountability

Of the 78 journals, 58 (74.4%) emphasised that authors are fully responsible and accountable for all AI-assisted content; 8 journals were unclear on this matter; and the remaining 12 journals did not directly comment on the authors' accountability regarding AI-generated content. Among the top 25 journals, 13 out of 16 (81.2%) with AI policies mentioned the authors' accountability for AI-generated content.

Transparency and disclosure

Of the 78 journals, 69 (88.5%) required transparency and insisted on disclosure of the fact if authors had used AI. However, the journals differed in their recommendations on the specific section of the manuscript that should feature the disclosure: of the 69, 31 recommended the methods section; 16 stipulated

a separate section; 16 more recommended *either* the methods section *or* the acknowledgements; 5 recommended the acknowledgements; and one journal recommended the cover letter. Of the 16 that offered a choice, the choice was guided by the purpose for which AI had been used: if for help in writing, the acknowledgements were considered the appropriate place; if for help in formal research design and methods including data collection, analysis, or figure generation, it was the methods section.

Some journals required details of the specific AI tool used (name, version, and manufacturer) and how it was applied. Four journals recommended an additional disclosure of the use of AI in the cover letter at initial submission. Five journals, all published by the American Psychological Association, required

Table 2. Characteristics of 200 journals selected randomly from 578 journals listed under psychiatry and mental health and the top 25 journals in that domain

Characteristic	Randomly selected journals	Top 25 journals
Major publishers		
Elsevier	20	6
Springer Nature	19	3
Wiley	17	5
SAGE	13	–
Routledge	13	–
Cambridge University Press	10	1
Lippincott Williams & Wilkins	8	–
Taylor & Francis	7	2
American Psychological Association	7	–
Emerald Publishing	6	–
Other publishers	80	8
Country of origin		
United States	62	12
United Kingdom	61	12
The Netherlands	10	–
Switzerland	8	1
Germany	8	–
Spain	5	–
Brazil	4	–
Canada	4	–
India	4	–
Iran	4	–
Other countries	30	–

that the AI outputs be uploaded as supplementary material.

Among the top 25 journals, all 16 that included AI policies required transparency and disclosure regarding the use of AI. Of the 16, the recommended sections for disclosure were the methods section or a separate section (5 journals each), a choice between the methods section and the acknowledgements (3 journals), acknowledgements only (2 journals), and disclosure in “both the relevant text of the submitted work and the cover letter or email accompanying the submission” (1 journal).

Table 3. Policy elements covered by psychiatry and mental health journals that include policies on artificial intelligence (among the 200 randomly selected journals)

Policy element	Journals (n = 78)	
	Number	Proportion (%)
AI tool as a named author	69	88.5
Author accountability	58	74.4
Transparency and disclosure	69	88.5
Integrity concerns	14	17.9
Adaptability of policies	27	34.6
Prohibition on any use of AI	0	0.0
Peer review	49	62.8
AI-generated images	55	70.5
AI-assisted copy editing	56	71.8
AI detection tools	0	0.0

AI: artificial intelligence.

Integrity concerns

Only 14 (17.9%) of the 78 journals addressed the potential impact of the use of AI on research integrity and ethics, and did so with

Table 4. Policy elements covered by psychiatry and mental health journals that include policies on artificial intelligence (among the top 25 journals)

Policy element	Journals (n = 16)	
	Number	Proportion (%)
AI tool as named author	16	100.0
Author accountability	13	81.2
Transparency and disclosure	16	100.0
Integrity concerns	4	25.0
Adaptability of policies	7	43.8
Prohibition of any use of AI	0	0.0
Peer review	9	56.2
AI-generated images	10	62.5
AI-assisted copy editing	8	50.0
AI detection tools	1	6.2

AI: artificial intelligence.

little consistency among them. For instance, some journals published by Mary Ann Liebert publishers mentioned that “potential biases and limitations of the outcomes of AI use should be discussed by the authors when presenting their results” and some journals published by Elsevier included the following cautionary note: “AI can generate authoritative sounding output that can be incorrect, incomplete, or biased.” Among the top 25 journals, 4 out of the 16 (25%) with AI policies addressed integrity concerns.

Adaptability of policies

Roughly a third (34.6%, or 27 out of 78) of the journals noted that AI policies would be updated periodically as AI is a rapidly advancing field. For example, two journals, published by Mary Ann Liebert publishers, stated that “the policies below will be reviewed and updated as technologies, best practices and ethical considerations in AI evolve.” However, the frequency of reviewing and updating policies was not stated in any of the journals. Among the top 25 journals, 7 of the 16 (43.8%) with AI policies commented on the adaptability of policies, with one journal specifying the frequency of updates (every 6 months or as necessary).

Policy on artificial intelligence–generated images

Policies on AI-generated images varied across journals. Roughly half of them (48.7%, or 38 out of 78) prohibited or restricted the use of AI-generated images, although 29 of them outlined specific exceptions under which such images could be permitted; 17 adopted a more flexible stance, allowing AI-generated images but mandating disclosure; and 23 provided no

information on AI-generated images within their AI policies.

The nature of exceptions varied with the publisher. Springer Nature journals permitted AI-generated images in some cases, such as artwork obtained from agencies with contractual agreements with the publisher and created through legally acceptable means or images referenced in content specifically discussing AI, subject to a case-by-case editorial review. Elsevier journals noted that exceptions may be made when AI is integral to the research design or methodology, for instance in AI-assisted imaging techniques used for generating or interpreting research data, such as in biomedical imaging. They also stated that AI-generated cover art could be allowed, provided prior approval is obtained from both the editor and the publisher. Emerald allowed the use of generative AI images for illustrative purposes within scholarly critique and discussion.

Among the top 25 journals, 10 of the 16 (62.5%) with AI policies included a policy on AI-generated images. Eight journals prohibited or restricted the use of AI images, although six of them outlined specific exceptions. The remaining two journals adopted a more flexible stance, allowing AI-generated images but requiring disclosure.

Artificial intelligence–assisted copy editing

Artificial intelligence–assisted copy editing was allowed by 56 of the 78 journals (69.2%), of which 15 required that such use be disclosed, whereas the rest did not mandate a disclosure; 22 journals did not explicitly mention a policy on this. Among the top 25 journals, 50%

of journals with AI policies included a policy on AI-assisted copy editing.

Peer review

The use of AI in peer review was either prohibited or restricted by 47 of the 78 journals (60.3%). Most of them advised reviewers not to upload manuscripts into generative AI tools. Two journals were less restrictive but required disclosure of the use of AI. Some journals, particularly those published by Springer Nature or Elsevier, mentioned that they are currently exploring safe and compliant AI tools for reviewers, and may update policies accordingly. Among the top 25 journals, 9 of the 16 (56.25%) journals with AI policies addressed the use of AI in peer review.

Tools for detecting the use of artificial intelligence

None of the 200 randomly selected journals mentioned whether they use AI detection tools. Only one of the top 25 journals (published by BMJ Publishing Group) reported using AI detection tools.

Discussion

Our study revealed that only 39% of the journals in the field of psychiatry and mental health that formed the basis of our data have adopted formal policies regulating the use of AI. This small proportion raises major concerns about the integrity and accountability of scientific papers published in this field since the popularisation of AI chatbots. It is noteworthy that this percentage is remarkably lower than that reported for journals in some other disciplines such as ophthalmology (63.1%)¹⁵ and dentistry (70.9%).²¹ In parallel with the present study, Tran et al. reviewed the top 100 psychiatry and mental health journals

on SCImago and found that 91% addressed the use of AI in their instructions to authors; 22% allowed AI-generated content; and 18% permitted AI-generated images.²² Our lower estimate (39% versus 91%) likely reflects that our sample spans all quartiles, rather than only top-ranked journals. As journal policies keep evolving, repeating this study in the future could chart the progress made in this respect.

We found that higher-ranking journals were more likely to employ AI policies, with 56% of the Q1 journals versus only 20% of the Q4 journals including a policy on AI. This finding aligns with observations in other disciplines.^{15,23,24} Affiliation with a major publisher, more frequent policy updates, and stronger editorial awareness on AI policies are some possible reasons for the higher-impact journals having AI policies. More importantly, these observations call for urgent updates to the author and reviewer guidelines in psychiatry and mental health journals, especially by the lower-quartile journals. We also observed that fewer journals originating from outside the United States and the UK included AI policies. Journals from low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) may face challenges in adopting AI policies, potentially because of limited familiarity with AI technologies among members of their editorial boards.

Greater standardisation of AI policies among academic journals will ensure consistency and fairness in approaching the use of AI in scholarship. However, given that the current guidelines from different committees, publishers, and journals show inconsistencies, it would be helpful for future researchers, editors, and reviewers to be able to refer to a consensus guideline on the use of AI. Efforts to this end are already in progress; for example, the

CANGARU initiative, a partnership between researchers, publishers including Elsevier, Springer Nature, and Wiley, and COPE, is working towards a single set of guidelines that would represent the consensus of the research community.²⁵

In relation to the themes of AI policies identified by Perkins and Roe,¹⁰ the most common themes covered in the reviewed guidelines were denying authorship to AI and transparency or disclosure. Awarding authorship to AI is currently not acceptable, largely due to the AI models' inability to be accountable for the content they generate. Although this remains the consensus of the scientific community, some dissenting opinions have also emerged. Because modern AI tools are capable of making substantial contributions to the conception and design of a study, analysis and interpretation of data, and drafting a manuscript, some scholars have argued that an AI tool can be allowed to be an author.²⁶ However, such views are unlikely to overturn the broader consensus against AI authorship. Increasingly, it is suggested that the debate should shift from whether AI deserves authorship to how it can best be integrated into the research and publication process, with transparent disclosure of its use.²⁷

Most journals with an AI policy commented on the authors' accountability for any AI-generated content. This aligns with the COPE guidance, namely that "authors are fully responsible for the content of their manuscript, even those parts produced by an AI tool."⁸ As AI chatbots are known to 'hallucinate' (generate false or misleading information) and to provide incomplete or biased responses, it is crucial that authors carefully review any AI-generated content for accuracy and appropriateness.²⁸

Most journals with an AI policy required disclosure of AI use, but differed substantially on where within the text of a research paper the disclosure should appear. Most journals prefer either the methods section or the acknowledgements, whereas some journals indicated that the location depends on the purpose for which AI is used, namely whether for help in writing or in formal research design and methods. And although this recommendation aligns with the ICMJE guidelines, only a few journals followed the additional ICMJE recommendation for disclosure in the cover letter at submission.⁷ These differences may reflect differences in the structure of manuscripts across journals. Sixteen journals recommended a separate section disclosing the use of AI, and, given the rising use of AI, other journals may need to follow suit.

Some journals in this analysis acknowledged that these policies may be revised in the future. This acknowledgement is important given the rapid advances in AI. Peer review policies may be a case in point: although current guidance discourages the use of AI in peer review, several journals noted that policies could change if safe and compliant tools emerge. Reviewers are currently prohibited from uploading manuscripts onto AI tools owing to concerns of confidentiality, and that will continue to be a barrier. However, if journals develop assistive AI tools that preserve confidentiality, the peer review process could be streamlined, potentially increasing the pool of reviewers and helping editors manage the rising submission volumes.²⁹⁻³¹ For example, AI tools capable of flagging potential errors and inaccuracies could help reviewers and editors efficiently identify problems in the manuscripts that could otherwise be overlooked.

Although Perkins and Roe identified integrity concerns as a separate theme within academic publishers' guidelines on AI, these concerns were not widely reflected within the journals we reviewed.¹⁰ When AI is used in the research process, it is important not only to disclose its use but also to acknowledge and discuss any limitations or biases it may introduce. It may be important to include in the submission guidelines a cautionary note to authors on the potential risks to research integrity that the use of AI may pose.

A notable proportion of journals permitted the use of AI-assisted copy editing, reflecting a growing acceptance of AI tools for language support in academic publishing.³² However, practices surrounding transparency varied considerably: some journals required explicit disclosure of AI use for copy editing, whereas others allowed such use without mandating disclosure. This inconsistency suggests that although the use of AI for improving language and grammar is becoming normal, there remains a lack of consensus on whether such use should be declared. Also, it may be hard to draw a line between AI-assisted copy editing and the use of AI for substantive editing, which improves human-written text by going beyond the mechanics (spelling, grammar, punctuation, usage, style, and consistency) to introduce new ideas and content.

Despite growing concerns about the misuse of generative AI in scholarly publishing, explicit mention of AI detection tools in journal policies remains rare. Among the 200 randomly selected journals for the present study, none referred to the use of AI detection software, and only one journal among the top 25 explicitly stated that such tools were being used. There are many limitations and risks associated with the use of AI detection tools

that may have led to journals being cautious about adopting them. Firstly, the validity and reliability of AI detectors in distinguishing human-written texts from AI-generated texts have been called into question.^{33,34} AI tools may learn how to outpace AI detectors much more quickly than the pace at which detection tools can be created or updated.³⁵ Secondly, concerns have been raised about potentially compromising authors' intellectual property and confidentiality by exposing submissions to open AI systems to detect AI-generated text.³⁶ Moreover, AI detectors may introduce biases, for instance, by disproportionately flagging the work of non-native speakers of English as potentially written by AI.³⁷ Costs and lack of familiarity with AI detection tools may be other contributory reasons.

Certain applications of AI, such as generating research ideas or supporting brainstorming, are inherently difficult to detect and regulate. In such cases, reliance on author disclosure becomes critical. However, as AI-generated content becomes more sophisticated and increasingly indistinguishable from human writing, it is becoming increasingly difficult to adapt and effectively use AI detection tools to identify undisclosed AI use. In an era of burgeoning scientific fraud,³⁸ the need for clear and enforceable policies as well as educational efforts to promote ethical AI use is critical. However, it should be borne in mind that the risk of unethical and improper use of AI would persist even if every journal adopted strict policies; hence, the onus is on researchers to not use AI inappropriately.

Although AI policies are relevant across scientific disciplines, they hold particular importance for psychiatry and mental health research. This field often involves vulnerable

populations, sensitive data, and research findings with direct clinical implications. Inadequate supervision of the use of AI could lead to misrepresentation of patient experiences, distort evidence that guides clinical practice, and perpetuate biases embedded in the training data. Clear journal policies on the use of AI are therefore especially vital to safeguard the integrity and credibility of psychiatry and mental health research.

Limitations

Reviewing all 578 journals, rather than selecting a sample, would have yielded more precise findings. However, a sample was used for reasons of feasibility, and the chosen sample size was deemed sufficient to provide estimates within acceptable margins of error. It should also be acknowledged that many journals – particularly from the LMICs – are not indexed in SCImago; the uptake of AI policies in these journals, which is likely to be considerably lower, was therefore not captured in this study. Furthermore, some journals listed under the psychiatry and mental health category in SCImago are not specifically focused on these fields (for example, *The Lancet Regional Health – South-East Asia* and *LGBT Health*), which may limit the specificity of the findings.

Some journals may require disclosure of the use of AI within the online submission system rather than in the manuscript itself; however, we did not assess submission-system requirements—our analysis was limited to information in author and reviewer guidelines that were publicly available.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of our study, we make the following recommendations

to researchers, editors, publishers, and policymakers.

1. All psychiatry and mental health journals should provide clear policies on the use of AI as part of their guidelines for authors and reviewers to align with the recommendations by COPE and ICMJE.
2. Within the guidelines for authors, AI policies should include clear and comprehensive information on authorship being limited only to humans, the accountability of authors, disclosure and transparency, potential risks to integrity, adaptability of policies, specific policies on AI-generated images, AI-assisted copy editing, and other specific constraints and exclusions as appropriate for each journal.
3. Journals with lower impact, those based in non-English-speaking countries, and those not affiliated to major publishers need to take proactive steps to update their guidelines for authors and reviewers to incorporate policies on the use of AI.
4. Journals should update their AI policies regularly to reflect any advances occurring in AI technology and any changes to international guidelines such as those of COPE and ICMJE. Editorials may be a useful way to bring such updates to the attention of researchers.
5. Steps should be taken globally within academia to raise awareness of the ethics of, and practices related to, the use of AI in academic writing and peer review. Academic institutions such as universities have a key role in educating and training students and researchers at all levels in the ethical use of AI.

6. Psychiatric associations at international, regional, and local levels including the World Psychiatry Association and the Royal College of Psychiatrists should organise conferences, workshops, and professional development activities on the ethical use of AI in academic publishing to raise awareness on this topic among psychiatrists and other mental health professionals.
7. Publishers, journals, and academic associations should strengthen the ongoing efforts to develop AI detection tools that give more valid and reliable results while ensuring cost-effectiveness and accessibility.
8. Journals and publishers should invest more in developing safe AI tools to assist peer review without compromising the confidentiality of submitted work and update their policies on the use of AI.

As AI continues to permeate throughout academic research and publishing, psychiatry and mental health journals must develop and implement clear, transparent, and adaptable policies regarding the use of AI. Aligning with guidelines from COPE and ICMJE, investing in reliable AI detection tools, and educating or training stakeholders on the ethical use of AI will be the key steps in ensuring ethical and high-quality scholarly publishing.

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